

Factors Influencing International Student's Choice of Business as Program of Study in Zhejiang Province, China

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Abstract

Education is the primary agent of transformation towards sustainable development. It increases people's capacities to transform their visions for society into reality. All countries strive for quality education for their sustainable development. Business programs has been highlighted as of great importance in moulding the performance of students in schools worldwide. This study therefore investigated the Factors Influencing International Student's Choice of Business as Program of Study in Zhejiang Province, China. The study employed a descriptive survey design. The target population was 2,000 students in the Zhejiang Province, China. The study used a sample of 100 students From Zhejiang Province, China. Data was collected by the use of questionnaire for students. The data was then analyzed quantitatively and presented using frequencies, mean and standard deviation. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to aid in generating a summary of results which were represented in tabular form. It can be concluded that in investigating the factors that influence International students' in choosing business as a program if study in Zhejiang province, China, some factors cannot be exempted. Among these major factors are the parental factors that influence international students' choice of business as a program of study, students' perception and career choice. From the findings, it gives the researchers the reason to settle that parents have no influence on students' choice of business as a program of study. However, students' have positive perception about business program and that their career choice also has influence on their choice of business as a program of study.

Keywords: Business program, parental factors, students' perception, students' career choice

INTRODUCTION

Business studies have been receiving much attention from both the business community and students. Business education involves teaching students the fundamental theories and processes of business. Business education in this field occurs at several levels including tertiary education.

Business education is one of the most crucial factors that help students to achieve the following goals: gaining the knowledge of business concept through the study of different business subjects, to achieve business, financial, economic, and digital literacy and also develop technological skill that help in the overall productivity of the organization. Business education brings various advantages in different sectors of business for the purpose of proper management. However, it seems that there have been many factors that have influence students' choice of business as a program of study.

Education is recognized all over the world as the backbone to national development which prepares the human resources to fulfill the manpower needs of a nation (Lambert, 1997). This explains why nations invest in education to develop its human resources. The business study which was earlier referred to as Business education was introduced into Public High Schools in the U.S.A by tax payer's demand during last part of the nineteenth century. Parents insisted that public schools should provide business education, otherwise they would take their children to private business colleges (Ogelevon, 1997). Many district schools introduced Business education courses such as, Shorthand, Typewriting and Book keeping. Since then, Business education has been undergoing scrutiny and transformation (Popham, Keller, Moulding, Pellegrino & Sandifer, 2005). For example, high school teachers in both US and New Zealand have low opinions of business as a career opportunity relative to Medicine and Engineering as a consequence (Wells & Fieger, 2006). In Nigeria, (Awofala, 2012) Business Studies in Junior Secondary Schools' curriculum came about as a means of laying the foundation for national technological and economic advancement, as articulated in the National Policy on Education (Federal Ministry of Education, 2011).). According to John Hubert Cornyn, "business education in

its broad perspective is the means of educating the students with regards to creating awareness of business and economic problems in society". Business studies is a very important course that prepares students towards their future career or profession (Kotler, 2003). The study of business education is now widespread in this era. Within a period of time, Business studies has been introduced in tertiary institutions in many countries like Japan, United States, Thailand, Malaysia and China because of the value placed on it. Business education comprises subject areas such as Accounting, Business Management, Cost Accounting, Economics, and others at the tertiary level. Over the years, there have emerged numerous public and private institutions which now offer certificates in degree and diploma in business education. In Nigeria, the choice of business tends to rank low among other professional courses like Medicine, Engineering, Economics and others (Crews & Dickerson, 1977).

Education in China, started from the Revolution of 1911, He Ziyuan (1865-1941) and Qiu Fengjia (1864-1912), successfully established some Western-style schools, such as Yunandong Primary School (in 1885), Tongren School (1888) and Xingmin School (1903) in Guangdong Province in the late 19th century, symbolizing the birth of Chinas modern education. However, business studies also started informally by the European merchants who came to Africa and established business organizations. These Europeans offered on the job training to their staff in Accounting, Secretarial Duties with some amount of Management Skills (Sifuna & Otiende 2006). In addition, Chinese society also looks at business studies as "number crunchers", that is, there is an emphasis upon numerical accuracy, routine recording and calculation methods, together with attention to detail (Kotler, 2003). The workload in business profession could influence students to shift into other professions (McDowall & Jackling, 2010). Many researchers conducted have considered the factors affecting students' career choice in business (Checci, Daniele, Japelli, & Tullio, 2003; Kotler, 2003).

A study conducted by (Dibabe, T.M. Wubie, A. W. Wondmagegn, 2015) shows that the difficulty of the program has a significant negative effect on students' choice of business programs. Accounting and finance courses combinations are heavily theoretical and quantitative, therefore most students believed that these courses are difficult. As a result, most students have withdrawn from the program because their quality does not match with the skills which are required by these courses. But a study conducted by (Massa & Karlsson, 2018) shows that the difficulty of the program has no significant effect on students' choice of business programs. According to the finding of Azevedo and Sugahara (2012) cited in (Mbawuni & Nimako, 2015), creativity has a significant negative effect on students in choosing business as a major. It shows that students who have strong creativity are not willing to join the accounting profession because they see accounting to be less creative than other professions. However, in the study of (Harnovinsah, 2017) citing the finding of Britt (2012) shows that creativity has a significant positive effect on students in choosing business as a program of study.

Often there are many factors that influence student in choosing their program of study. (Gifford & Nilsson, 2014) citing Zhang (2010) in his research identifies such factors to include cultural, sociological and personal factors. Also,(Odia & Ogiedu, 2013) stated in his study that during the late 1990's, students who read business major declined in number of enrollments which was attributed to many factors such as perilous future career and corporates scandals (Albrecht & Sack 2007). There are more views concerning the positive and negative effects that are associated with choosing business as a program of study. It was against this background that the study seeks to examine the factors that influence students' choice of business program of study in Zhejiang province, China.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Since the inception of business education in the early part of the 20th century, the discipline was shaped by the forces of the market place. Business education was not created based on research and scientific methods, but it evolved based on industry procedures and practices that were later compiled into business theory and textbooks (Pierson, 1959). In the post-world war II era, there was strong demand for business graduates driven by the business expansion that occurred, which intensified the need for business managers. In the study of (Nino,

2011), Pierson (1959) found that the most acute problem in business education was the lack of strong academic standards needed to produce scholarly graduates at the four-year college level. The challenges then were that the business field was new, and the daily aspects of business careers had remote connections to academic work that was taught at the college level. But the need for graduates was high, and enrollment in business school was burgeoning, which decreased the incentive for business schools to enforce standards on business curriculum when the market was not demanding them. Using the analytical lenses of (Rhoades, 2006) and drawing on the theory of “Academic Capitalism,” it is easy to see the influence of the market on business education and the unintended consequences that can occur from it.

In 1959, the Ford Foundation sponsored a study on business education that was co-authored by Robert A. Gordon and James Howell in 1959. Notably, the Ford Foundation initiated the study after Henry Ford II formed an advisory board consisting of intellectuals in that era to help advise on management issues in his grandfather’s ailing company. Management education was becoming an important transformative science for businesses at that time. (Goodrick, 2002) cited in his study Gordon and Howell (1959) in their findings emphasized the changes that were needed in business education, including raising the quality of business students and faculty, and making the business curriculum more intellectual and relevant to management (Khurana, 1997). Also, Pierson (1959) noticed that the curriculum boundaries between two-year and four-year colleges were nebulous, and so he made recommendations for both programs. He suggested that two-year programs should emphasize training in the simpler business skills and preparation in the elementary aspects of the background subjects of business. He also recommended that the four-year colleges should emphasize 1) the application of general knowledge by building a foundation in non-business subjects such as statistics, psychology, economics, and sociology, 2) the study of the application of the broad functional disciplines such as finance, marketing, accounting and production, and 3) study of management at the different levels of the firm. In the study of (Molly J.Wickam, 2015) It was after the Gordon and Howell report and Pierson’s study that the American Assembly of Collegiate Schools of Business (AACSB) developed curricular standards for the field requiring students to take up to 60% of their coursework in the liberal arts area (Mason, 1990). The American Assembly of Collegiate Schools of Business mandate characterized a movement away from vocationalism and more toward the liberal arts foundation for business graduates. The challenge in this strong weave between business and education is that academia was not pioneering the transformation in business; it was the market.

Parents’ influence on students’ choice of business as a program of study

There is an important factor that affects students’ achievement, their future study, and major choice which is parental or family members’ influence, particularly, in the context of Arab countries. But studies conducted in this field showed inconsistent results. (Simons et al., 2004) cited Cohen and Hanno (1993), found that parents, counselors, and friends’ influences does not generally affect the students’ decision. Also, (Rababah, 2016) in his study cited Sharifah and Tinggi (2013) revealed that parents’ influence did not affect the students’ decision. In contrast, Mazzarol and Soutar (2002) reached the conclusion that family members, peers, and advisors (teachers, agents, and seniors) may have a hand in influencing the choice of the major selected by students. Again, Pimpa (2007), in the study of “influence of normative referents on Thai students’ choice of international education”, found that while parents do influence the choice of business major, those who choose accounting as their majors were not influenced.

Additionally, students’ major choices can also be influenced by the occupation held by their parents. Students whose parents own and operate small businesses may want or feel obligated to follow in their parents’ footsteps (Zody, 2006). Students may consider the ease of life that is available to them because a job would be available to them right out of school, they could hold a high position within the business, and there is a possibility that they might own and operate the business one day. However, children of family business owners often have more experience with how the business world operates. These students have often worked in the family

business their whole life, experiencing all of what their parents went through in the day-to-day operations of the business.

Perception as a factor that influences student choice of business as a program of study

Accounting education has been the subject of considerable debates since 1980s. Prior researches document that introductory Accounting students have negative perception of accounting. Accounting is attractive to the students in terms of profession but the “negative views regarding the nature and role of accounting persist (Fisher & Murphy, 1995, p.58). Society’s perception of the legitimacy of the accounting profession and its members is grounded in the verbal and visual images of accountants that are projected not only by accountants themselves but also by the media. How accountants are portrayed in media have a significant impact on the accounting profession. Typically, Accountants have been referred to as number crunchers, focusing on numerical accuracy, routine recording and calculation methods. Abrecht & Sack (2000), Cory (1992), Garner and Dombrowski (1997), attribute the negative perception to misinformation or lack of information about accounting and the duties performed by accountants. To date, (SAMSURI et al., 2016) stated in their study that efforts by professional accounting bodies and firms to change the negative and inaccurate perception of accountancy and accountants have yielded limited success (Jackling & Calero, 2006). (Molloy, 2009) in his study that Byrne and Willis (2005), maintain that the public view of accountants is generally negative and that this perception might discourage potential students from studying the program. Similarly, Cohen & Hanno (1993) found that the perception of accounting as boring and excessively number oriented might lead student to choose other majors than accounting. Furthermore, the traditional view of accounting as involving precision and order has been found to drive creative people away from the profession. In addition, many bright young people are seeking careers in professional fields other than accounting as a result of the poor image of the accounting profession (Saemann & Crooker, 1999; Cohen & Hanno, 1993). The personal image of accountants and how they market themselves are more important than the price, product and ‘Smart’. Anyone whose success depends upon or requires the cooperation of another individual or group needs a positive personal image. Unfortunately, high-quality students hardly ever perceive accountants as they perceive themselves. People regard accountants as boring, middle- aged men sitting in a back office with a calculator and a stack of files. As a consequence, the accounting profession does not always attract high quality students. Whether a person chooses to pursue an accounting career may be determined by the image of accountants in the media. Byrne & Willis (2005) find that perceptions of accounting are influenced by factual media. (Odia & Ogiedu, 2013) in his study stated that Mathus & Fowler (2009) find that the portrayal of accountants in the media could be recalled by the sampling group. Tan & Laswad (2009) in an extension of their 2006 study survey university students at the beginning and end of their degree. The comparisons between accounting and non-accounting students reveal that those who intended to major in accounting generally hold positive attitudes towards the accounting profession. Tan & Laswad (2009) found that a higher proportion of accounting students decide on their major prior to university study. Therefore, they recommended that the accounting profession should promote the positive aspects of accounting career not only to pre-university students but also to the public as this strategy would enhance the public profile of members of the profession.

In contrast, a study conducted by the Department of Accounting, Universiti Tenaga Nasional on accounting job outcomes indicated that student’s perceived accounting profession to provide positive job outcomes. The result was found to be consistent with the Mazlina and Hasmawi (2012). In other words, satisfaction, high income, high status and bright future are what students consider accounting profession to be.

Career choice as an influence in students’ choice of business as a program of study

The word career has been a derivative of French and Latin origin. Its simplest definition is given in the study of (Rao, 2017) by Geciki (2002) as the occupational, commercial or industrial activity that a person may adopt during his educational life or in some other part or till his death. Redman and Wilkinson (2001), clarifies career

as the application of a person's cognition and capabilities, providing command over profession, timely work expertise and a basis of developing and bettering business networks.

(Dr Ahmad Nahar Al-Rfou, 2013) in his study emphasized that Malgwi, Howe and Burnaby (2005), defined the factors influencing the choice of major as interest in the subject, job opportunities, compensation, introductory course and discussion with other students. Another study carried out by Uyar, Güngörmüş, and Kuzey (2011), found that the students who have a desire to work in Accounting field assumed that Accounting field provide good job opportunities, and the field matches with their abilities and interest while students who have no desire to work in the field of Accounting assumed that other fields provide wider job opportunities and are less stressful, tiring and tedious. (Siegall et al., 2007) cited in his study DeMarie and Aloise-Young (2003), finding that the reason for selecting a major for the business students are; career, the interest in the area and enjoyment of learning. (Dr Ahmad Nahar Al-Rfou, 2013), mentioned that the most factors influencing the choice of business major are earnings, career options, initial earnings and ability or aptitude. Collins and Giordani (2004) reported in their study that 68.4% of the respondents chose their major because they liked the kind of work it would enable them to do as compared to 7% who picked their major for its earning potential.

According to (Rababah, 2016) in his study cited that Markham & Kim (2002), there were studies in literature that showed students' choices for business as a major to be affected by the prestige, the job development, and the high earnings. They also declared that Job opportunities represent an important factor at influencing the students in choosing Accounting major (Ramadan, 1989), (Strasser, Ceyhun & Schroeder, 2002), and (Odia & Ogied, 2013). In addition to, (Baker et al., 2018), examine five factors which own the potential to influence the students in choosing the major, and those are: requirement policies to enter into the study of the major, job opportunities, college or university reputation, previous academic experiences, and courses' characteristics. According to some previous researchers, the job opportunities or the job perspectives consider the most significant factor to influence students' major selection

Ahmad Nahar Al- Rfou in his article "factors that influence the choice of business major evidence from Jordan". Redman and Wilkinson (2001) clarify career as the application of a person's cognition and capabilities, providing command over profession, tents gave more importance for future job factors; they agreed that the future earnings, career option, occupational prestige and type of work are the most important factors that affect the selection of Business major.

This study presents the following questions:

1. What are the parental factors influencing international student's choice of business program in Zhejiang province, China?
2. What are the influences of international student's perceptions about the choice of business program in the Zhejiang province, China?
3. What are the influences of career choice on the international student's choice of Business program in Zhejiang province, China?

Research Methodology

For this research, the methodology used is going to be the quantitative approach. In the quantitative approach, the questionnaire survey will be used as an instrument for collecting primary data from the research sample. The random sampling method will be applied in the study. In this part of the study, there is research conducted with the data obtained through the questionnaire form prepared for the studies. For the current research, the questionnaire is used as the tool for the study to collect the data. The questionnaire is adopted from previous studies. The questionnaire will include three sections; each section contains items and statements regarding every study variable. The Respondents will be required to fill up the questionnaire with a Likert scale point.

The target population for the study comprised all business students in Zhejiang province, China. Nevertheless, the accessible population consisted business students in Zhejiang province, China. These schools were selected due to their proximity to the researchers. In spite of their proximity, the schools have adequate population sample size of students to enable us carry out the research.

Through the (Krejcie and Morgan's 1970) table for choosing sample size in a given population, the one hundred accessible. Sampling will be done because in many cases, a complete coverage of the population is not possible (Sarantakos, 1998). To ensure that the sample is more representative of the population in each school, the proportionate stratified sampling technique was employed. This was done to ensure an equitable distribution of the sample size for the schools based on their respective population. The stratified technique was used specifically to ensure that proportionate number of males and females were obtained base on their population for the research. With this technique, the researchers identified the total population and appropriate sample size was determined.

Results

The reliability test is used to ensure that all the items of the questionnaire are consistent. According to the above table 1, the reliability test revealed the following conclusions: There is a great internal consistency among the variable parental factor's items with a Cronbach alpha value equal to 0.71. There is a great internal consistency among the variable Student's Perceptions items with a Cronbach alpha value equal to 0.72. There is a great internal consistency among the variable Career Choice items with a Cronbach alpha value equal to 0.71.

Table1: Summary of the Reliability Coefficient of the Items

Reliability of the Items	Reliability Coefficient	No. of Item
Parental factors influencing International student's choice of business program.	0.71	6
Influence of International Student's Perceptions About the Choice of Business Program	0.72	8
Influences of Career Choice on The International Student's Choice of Business Program	0.71	6

According to Fraenkel and Wallen (2000), the reliability coefficient should be at least 0.70 and preferably higher. Therefore, the reliability obtained is justifiable for the study.

For this research, the questionnaire is distributed to 100 people and 100 people responded, the response rate has been 100%.

The following table 2 displays the results of the respondents' profile, followed by some explanation.

Table 2: Profile of Respondents

	Frequency	Percentages
Gender		
Male	72	72
Female	28	28
Age		
Below 20 years	6	6
21-30 years	72	72
above 31 years	22	22

Respondents were asked to determine their gender. Table 2 shows that a total 72 (72%) of the respondents' gender were male students, while 28 (28%) of them are female. Respondents were also asked to indicate their age group or category. Table 3 also shows that the least (6%) of respondents belong to age group of below 20 years old, and 72 (72%) of the respondents belong to age group 21 to 30 years old, with age group above 31 at 22 (22%).

The following table 3 displays the results of the descriptive statistics followed by some explanations.

Table 3: Parental influence

Questions	Responses				
	No.		%		
	SD	D	N	A	SA
I choose to pursue business because of my parents advised me to do so.	0	51	23	11	15
I choose to pursue business because my parents are working in the business field	7	59	12	20	2
I choose to pursue business because of my family's cultural and economic status influenced me.	7	53	15	21	4
I choose to pursue business because my parents earn higher income in the business.	8	35	17	33	6
If not for my parents, I would have chosen another course other than business.	14	59	17	7	1
My parents mounted pressure on me to choose business as a course.	25	55	14	6	0

Table 3 analyzed the views of the students on the extent to which parental factors influenced their choice of business as a program of study. Out of 100 respondents, 51(51%) of the students disagreed to the fact that their choice of business course was due to advices given by their parents. Nonetheless, 26(26%) of the students agreed to the fact that their choice of business was as a result of parental advise. It seems that student's choice of business as a program of study was not dependent on parental advice. This is in agreement with Sharifah and Tinggi (2013) finding that parents' influence did not affect student's decision. Again, 66 (66%) respondents disagreed on choosing business program because their parents are working in the field of business as opposed to 22(22%) of respondents who agreed that they chose business course because their parents are working in the business field. In the same way, Zody (2006) in his study brought to light that students whose parents own and operate small businesses may want or feel obligated to follow in their parents' footsteps. Thus, the finding of Zody (2006) was not in agreement with the views of the respondents. With regards to family culture and economic status, 60(60%) of the respondents disagreed to choosing business because of that while 25(25%) agreed to this count.

In addition, on the issue of higher income earnings of parents in the business field, the results indicated that 43(43%) of the respondents disagreed as compared to 39 (39%) who agreed to choosing business as a program of study by virtue of their parents' higher income earnings in the business field. Moreover, pertaining to students choosing business because their parents pressed them to do so, 6 (6%) agreed as opposed to 80(80%) of the respondents. Furthermore, 73(73%) of the respondents disagreed to the issue of choosing a course other than business because of their parents whereas 8 (8%) of the students agreed they would have chosen a different course if not for their parents.

It is concluded from the results that on the average, majority of the respondents disagreed and minority of the respondents agreed to choosing Business program by reason of the influence of their parents. This implies that parents actually do not have influence on the student's choice of Business as a program of study. The results of the study are evident in finding of Cohen and Hanno (1993) that parents, counselors and friends' influence do not generally affect students' decision. Also, the results of the study support the finding of Sharifah and Tinggi (2013) that parents' influence does not affect students' decision. In another study conducted by

Olaosebikan and Olusakin (2014), it was found out that, on the average 21.5% of the respondents agreed that their parents' line of business influenced their career choice while 78.5% disagreed.

Table 4: Perception of students on Business Program

Questions	Responses				
	No.	%			
	SD	D	N	A	SA
I choose to pursue business because the field matches with my abilities.	2	6	11	59	22
I choose to pursue business because I enjoy doing calculations.	3	8	19	56	14
I choose to pursue because I prefer abstract thinking to rote memorization.	2	3	27	54	14
I choose to pursue business because people in the business field such as Accountants, Managers, Auditors etc. are highly respected	3	6	23	58	10
I choose to pursue business because business offers a wider range of job opportunities.	5	1	12	58	23
I choose to pursue business because those in the business field have high standard of living.	4	6	19	57	13
I choose to pursue business because the course promotes critical thinking.	3	5	13	63	16
I choose to pursue business because the course is not difficult.	10	62	18	10	0

Table 4 examined the International students' perception of Business program as a factor influencing their choice of program of study. As revealed by the table, 71 (71%) of the respondents were of the view that they chose business because the field matches with their abilities in contrast to 8 (8%) of the respondents who did not. Again, 70 (70%) of the respondents agreed to the fact that they chose business because they enjoy doing calculation while 11 (11%) did not. Also, 68 (68%) of the respondents chose Business program because they prefer abstract thinking to rote memorization rather than 5 (5%) of the respondents who did not prefer abstract thinking to rote memorization. Considering the pursuit of Business due to the fact that people in the business fields such as Accountants, Managers, Auditors, etc. are highly respected, 68(68%) of the respondents agreed to the fact that they chose to pursue business but 9(9%) disagreed. Regarding the issue of choosing business because business offers a wider range of job opportunities, 6(6%) of the respondents disagreed while 81(81%) of the respondents agreed to this view. The table further reveals that 70 (70%) chosen business because those in the business field have high standard of living as opposed to 10(10%) of the respondents who disagreed to this fact. More so, 79 (79%) choose to pursue business because the program promotes critical thinking and the remaining 8(8%) of the respondents disagreed to this fact. Lastly, 10 (10%) chose business because the program is easy whereas 72 (72%) disagreed to this view.

From the findings, it can be deduced that, perception of business program has a bearing on students' choice of business as a program of study. With majority of number of the respondents asserting to this fact in contrast to minority, the implication is that students' have a positive perception about Business program.

Also, the results of the study are congruent with the finding of Khalid (2016) that students have positive perceptions towards accounting profession like the general public.

Table 5: Career choice in the field of Business

Questions	Responses				
	No.		%		
	SD	D	N	A	SA
I choose to pursue business because there is high demand for business literates.	4	5	17	67	7
I choose to pursue business because working in the field is not risky.	11	65	17	7	0
I choose to pursue business because I have the passion to work in the business field.	0	0	10	69	21
I choose to pursue business because it leads to career self-actualization.	0	2	9	66	23
Career in business provides financial satisfaction.	1	6	13	57	23
Career in business will help me occupy high positions.	2	8	25	55	10

Table 5 depicts the results concerning how career choices of International students influence their choice of business as a program of study. From the study 74 (74%) of the respondents agreed to the fact that they chose to pursue business because there is high demand for business literates. Nonetheless, 9(9%) of the respondents disagreed that they chose business because there is high demand for business literates. Also, concerning choosing to pursue Business because working in the business field is not risky, out of 100 respondents 7 (7%) of the respondents agreed while 76(76%) of the respondents disagreed to this fact. Furthermore, 90(90%) of the respondents chose to pursue business because of the passion they have for working in the business field.

In addition, 89(89%) chose to pursue Business because they believe it leads to career self-actualization whereas, 2(2%) of the respondents disagreed to the fact that they chose business because it leads to career self-actualization.

Moreover, 80(80%) of the respondents agreed to choosing Business because careers in business provide financial satisfaction while 7(7%) of the respondents disagreed that they chose business because careers in business provide financial satisfaction. Considering the fact that careers in Business promises to help people acquire high positions in an organization, 65(65%) agreed and 10(10%) of the respondents were not of the same view. It is concluded from the results that on the average majority of the respondents agreed and minority of them disagreed to the fact that career choice of students has influence on their choosing Business as a program of study. This implies that career choice has influence on International student's choice of business as a program of study.

(Jaradat et al., 2017) in his study evidenced the findings of Malgwi, Howe and Burnaby (2005) who found out that the factors influencing the choice of major as interest in the subject, job opportunities, compensation, introductory course and discussion with other students. Also, in another study carried out by Uyar, Güngörmüş and Kuzey (2011), it was found that the students who have a desire to work in Accounting field assumed that Accounting field provides good job opportunities, and the field matches with their abilities and interest while students who have no desire to work in the field of Accounting assumed that other fields provide wider job opportunities and are less stressful, tiring and tedious.

Discussion

The study sets out to determine the critical factors which influence International students in choosing business as a program of study in Zhejiang Province, China. The study was guided by three specific objectives which include: to determine parental factors influencing International student choice of business as a program of study, to investigate the perception about business education and their choice of program of study, and to examine how

career choices influence International students' choice of business as a program study in Zhejiang Province, China. To achieve the purpose, descriptive research design was adopted for the study. The study employed quantitative approaches through the use of self- developed questionnaires. In all 100 students were selected for the study using simple random sampling technique. The obtained quantitative data analysis was done using descriptive (frequencies and percentages).

Research question one which find out the parental factors that influence international students' choice of business program revealed that students' choice of business as a program of study was not as a result of parental advice.

Research question two centered on the influence of International students' perceptions about the choice of business course in Zhejiang Province, China. The results showed that majority of the students have a positive influence towards their choice of business as a program of study.

The final research question was on the influence of career choice on the International students' choice of business program in Zhejiang province, China. The results indicated the career choice has influence on International students choosing business as a program of study.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that in investigating the factors that influence International students' in choosing business as a program if study in Zhejiang province, China, some factors cannot be exempted. Among these major factors are the parental factors that influence international students' choice of business as a program of study, students' perception and career choice. From the findings, it gives the researchers the reason to settle that parents have no influence on students' choice of business as a program of study. However, students' have positive perception about business program and that their career choice also has influence on their choice of business as a program of study.

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